

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Knowledge Level about Management of Social Media Use during the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

Introduction: Pandemic COVID-19 has led people to a new norm of spending most of their time at home. Regular direct physical social interactions become less common and replaced by interacting using social media.

Method: This study is a descriptive survey, describing society's knowledge on the management of social media usage in COVID-19 Pandemic. 666 samples were gathered who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Google Form was spread amongst webinar participants, processed and distributed into tables, including average score based on age groups.

Results: Majority of the participants (69.5%) achieved a score between 5-6 out of 7 questions that were given. Whilst, 0 participants received scores between 0 to 1. Results achieved by all age groups are almost similar, with age 36-40 appearing on top.

Conclusion: Knowledge regarding social media usage management does not appear to be affected by the person's age. This is because social media has been used by people of all ages, hence have almost similar knowledge regarding its usage.

Keywords: Low Birth Weight; Risk Factors; Chronic Energy Deficiency; Maternal Age; Antenatal Care Visits

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 outbreak has an impact on all corners of the world, including in Indonesia. Data shows that Indonesia currently has more than 3,194,733 positive confirmed cases as of July 26, 2021, with 84,766 of them dead. DKI Jakarta is a province with 794,937 confirmed cases, which is 24.9% of the total cases, followed by West Java (18.0%) and East Java (11.2%) [1].

Circumstances force people to adopt new norms to minimize direct human contact, including social distancing and working from home, or more commonly known as Work from Home (WFH) [2]. Daily social activities are also hampered, so the use of social media is among the best solutions to stay in touch while implementing new norms. Social media is an internet platform that emphasizes human interaction, which makes it easier for individuals to communicate, share

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and form online communities without the need to meet face-to-face [16]. The use of social media has a significant value in maintaining positive relationships among friends [3].

Kemp [4] obtained data showing that the use of social media in Indonesia increased by 10 million users, namely 6.8% during 2020-2021. It was found that the average Indonesian people spend 3 hours 14 minutes a day using social media. Most social media users are in the age range of 25 to 34 years, where the percentage of men is 14.8% and women 15.2%. The use of social media in people with an age range of 18 to 24 years is also high, with a percentage of 15.9% for men and 14.8% for women [4]. Although social media is a solution for communication without requiring direct contact and implementing new norms, long-term use of social media can have a negative impact, especially on psychological well-being [5]. With the increasing number of users, the risk of the number of people experiencing the adverse effects of social media also increases.

In adolescents social media has a small negative impact on overall well-being [6]. The negative impact experienced by adolescents, generally experienced because they spend a lot of time on social media, is that they are more prone to anxiety and depressive moods [7].

Educational activities using the webinar platform via Zoom are very important because the Indonesian people have a very small interest in reading, which is 0.001%. Public education through video media or webinars has proven to be effective in people of all age groups [8,9]. Therefore, we are interested in carrying out education related to how to use social media properly in the era of the COVID-19 pandemic.

2. Material and methods

This study is a descriptive survey study to assess the level of public's knowledge on the management of social media usage during the COVID-19 pandemic. This study was conducted on July 11, 2021 through an online webinar broadcasted through Zoom Meeting and Youtube. Sampling method that was used is total sampling. The online webinar is open to the public throughout Indonesia. Knowledge test were handed out to the webinar participants via Zoom meeting, live Youtube and participants' Whatsapp groups. Inclusion criteria in this study includes willingness to fill out a google form and aged between 12 to 55 years. Meanwhile, the exclusion criteria were respondents who did not fill out the google form completely. Primary data obtained through the google form. The data includes name, age, gender and true or false questions in order to evaluate their knowledge on management of social media usage during the COVID-19 pandemic. The data is then processed, and shown in tables to describe the demographics characteristics, average result per age group and interval data.

3. Results and discussion

Demography characteristics from respondents show age, gender and last education. Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents by their age and gender. The youngest respondent aged 12 years old, while the oldest aged 55 years old. Majority of the respondents are between the age of 16 to 20 years old, with a total of 495 of respondents (74, 32%). The youngest age group in this study ranged between 12 to 15 years old with 56 respondents (8, 41%). The total respondents that filled the form is 666 with 596 of them women and 70 of them men.

Table 2 shows the average result achieved by each age group. Age group were divided into 9 groups, with a range of 4 years each. Average score were divided into 2 scales, which are out of 7 and out of a 100. Age group with the highest score is between 36 to 40 years old (65.71%), while the lowest is age between 12 to 15 years old (54.85%). Meanwhile, three different age groups have achieved the same average score (57.14%) There were no respondent aged between 46 to 50 years old.

Table 3 shows the interval data of the knowledge test, which is the total amount of respondent achieves their respective scores. 17 respondents achieved a perfect score. Majority of the respondent scores between 4 to 5, while no respondent scores between 0 to 1.

Nowadays social media have already penetrated our lives from education to health [10, 11]. 58% of 47 million Indonesian citizens that have smartphones are teenagers aged 14 to 17 years old [12]. In 2018, research conducted in the United States of America shows that a majority of adolescents (95%) have access to handphones at home [13]. This data is in accordance with our participant's target that can be seen to be focused on the age group 16 - 20 years old with 495 participants in total. Most of the attendees are around the age of 16 - 20 and 21 - 25 years old, where they are at the age of developing their sense of self [14]. That causes them to be susceptible to the negative sides of social media [15].

Women according to Demircioğlu and Göncü Köse [16] have a tendency to experience social media addiction when compared to men. Women emphasize more towards relationships than men and often use social media as a media of interaction. [17; 18]. Men on the other hand mainly use social media for entertainment and recreation, while women also use them for information [19].

In Indonesia, junior high school student (SMP) normally aged between 13-15 years old, while senior high school student (SMK/SMA) aged between 15 to 18 years old. According to Rules of Ministry of Education and Culture no. 14 year 2018 [20], the limit age of a senior high schoolers is 21 years old. Research conducted by Andarwati [21] regarding the usage of social media on second year high school students from SMA Negeri 9 Yogyakarta shows a high result, which is that 76% of students are counted as high category in social media use. This is caused because the majority of teenagers assume that the more active they are on social media, then the more they will look cool and trendy. Meanwhile, teenagers that do not have social media will look lame or not up to date [22]. Adolescents however, as one of the users of social media, are still not able to choose beneficial activities. They also have a tendency to be easily affected by their social life on social media, without looking whether the impact will be positive or negative [23]. Survey results from Association of Indonesian Internet Service Provider (APJII) [24] shows that the most used services accessed by internet users are chatting applications and social media that reach 89%, followed by search engines, looking at photos, emails and banking. The survey also shows that 79, 23% of internet users categorized by education are at S1/Diploma level [24].

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents' Characteristics, including Age and Gender

Demographics Characteristics	Respondent (n = 666)	
	f	%
Age (years old)		
12 - 15	56	8.41
16 - 20	495	74.32
21 - 25	97	14.56
26 - 30	7	1.05
31- 35	3	0.45
36 - 40	5	0.75
41 - 45	2	0.30
46 - 50	0	0
51 - 55	1	0.15
Gender		
Female	596	89.49
Male	70	10.51

Table 2 Average Knowledge Test Scores by Age Group

Age (years old)	Average Score	
	Scale out of 7	Scale out of 100
12 – 15	3.84	54.85
16 – 20	3.97	56.71
21 – 25	3.94	56.26
26 - 30	4.43	63.26
31 - 35	4	57.14
36 - 40	4.6	65.71
41 - 45	4	57.14
46 - 50	0	0
51 - 55	4	57.14

There has been no research so far on the knowledge level of social media use so far, but a survey has said that students have the highest knowledge regarding social media followed by housewives and consultants [25]. However our results show a difference where the highest score is achieved by the 36 - 40 years old age group. Media social have been used by everyone from every age group, and usually only differentiated by their tendency and the type of media they use [26]. That is why in Table 2. That shows the average knowledge test results categorized by age are all similar.

Generally all participants answered the knowledge test with a good result, which is almost the highest interval at 4-5 with 463 participants in total. There are no participants with no knowledge about social media use management, shown by 0-1 intervals have no participants. This is because social media use has reached the public in every age group from 10 to 70 years old and older shown by a survey conducted by APJII survey : 2019 - 2020 (Q2) (2020), it also shows that internet use has penetrated 73,7% of the public, which is a rapid increase when considering in 2018 it was still 64,8% [25].

Table 3 Knowledge Test Result Interval Data

Interval Score	Average Score
0 - 1	0
2 - 3	171
4 - 5	463
6 - 7	32

4. Conclusion

Generally, people have known the management of social media use as shown by the overall good results. Knowledge regarding social media use does not depend on age according to knowledge test data categorized by each age group. Social media users are not only young people, but also older people.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this study.

Statement of ethical approval

This study implemented the principle of Helsinki Declaration and followed basic principles of ethic.

Statement of informed consent

Inform consent was included in the first google formular page.

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